

Development of a Cylindrical Trigger Hodoscope for the COMET Experiment

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Abstract

Charged lepton flavour violation (CLFV) provides an experimental probe into new physics beyond the Standard Model. The COMET experiment at the Japan Proton Accelerator Research Complex (J-PARC) in Tokai, Japan will be using the highest intensity muon beam yet to search for muon to electron conversion, a CLFV process, with the best sensitivity so far. Taking a staged approach to this search, Phase-I of COMET will begin in 2024 with a planned single event sensitivity of 3×10^{-15} . In order to reach this sensitivity, a cylindrical trigger hodoscope detector (called the CTH detector) is being developed in order to trigger on high momentum electrons coming from conversion events and provide timing information with better than 1 ns precision. The CTH detector will be capable of operating in a high hit rate, high radiation environment. In preparation for the construction of the CTH detector, 100 MeV electron beam tests were performed at the Australian Synchrotron to characterise prototype CTH detector counters. The target timing resolution was achieved as well as no strong positional dependence in light yield observed along the counter, meeting the requirements for Phase-I in these characteristics.

1 The COMET Experiment

The COherent Muon to Electron Transition (COMET) experiment is searching for muon to electron conversion, an example of charged lepton flavour violation and a clear signature for physics beyond the Standard Model [1]. Several strategies employed in Phase-I to reach sensitivity of 3×10^{-15} :

- High statistics using world's most intense muon beam at J-PARC (also generates many low momentum backgrounds).
- Excellent momentum resolution < 200 keV/c (additional timing information for track reconstruction in drift chamber is needed to meet this).
- Background suppression (pulsed muon beam, cosmic ray veto, etc).

Shown in Figure 1, the cylindrical detector (CyDet) is main physics detector for COMET Phase-I, consisting of a cylindrical drift chamber (CDC) for tracking and momentum measurements, and a cylindrical trigger hodoscope (CTH) for suppressing low momentum backgrounds and providing additional timing information.

Figure 1: The CyDet system (a) is the main physics detector used to measure the electron products of stopped muons during COMET Phase-I. The CTH detector provides additional timing information for high momentum electrons, utilising four fold coincidence in its concentric rings of scintillator counters as a trigger condition (b).

2 The CTH Detector

The main purpose of the CTH detector is to suppress low momentum backgrounds and provide timing information with < 1 ns resolution for signal measurements. The CTH detector consists of two sets of 64 concentric scintillator counter rings at either end of the CDC to record hits from electrons produced by stopped muons at the centre of the CyDet detector. Figure 2 gives an overview of a single counter. A tilted support structure for the scintillator counters is optimised for signal electron acceptance. Each counter is readout by 5-10 m optical fibre bundles which are used to remove multi-pixel photon counters (MPPC) from the high radiation dose area in the detector solenoid region (1×10^{12} neutrons cm^{-2} and 1 kGy gamma irradiation expected over 150 day data collection). A 1-10 MHz single hit rate is expected due to intense muon beam so short pulses in electronics readout (preamplifier shown in Figure 3) are required to avoid pile up. The CTH detector counters also require a photon yield of > 40 photons at output to account for reductions induced by neutron irradiation, fibre attenuation, etc. This has been previously measured in [2].

Figure 2: An overview of a single CTH counter readout system. Scintillation photons are transported via an optical fibre bundle to a multi-pixel photon counter (MPPC). This signal is then amplified and shaped by the CTH readout electronics before timing and energy information is sent to the trigger system.

Figure 3: Schematic overview of CTH preamplifier, the first stage of the CTH readout electronics. All four readout channels of a single MPPC photodetector are amplified and summed into a single output.

Figure 4: Normalised waveform output from CTH preamplifier during beam tests with 100 MeV electrons. Further signal shaping will be performed by second stage of CTH readout electronics in final detector.

3 Measurements at The Australian Synchrotron

Characterisation measurements of CTH counter prototypes were performed at the Australian Synchrotron using single 100 MeV electrons extracted from the linear accelerator (LINAC). Evaluation of timing resolution and positional dependence of the counters were performed by collecting waveforms for coincident hits in main and trigger counters (see normalised shape in Figure 4) at different positions (see Figure 5). Results show < 1 ns timing resolution is achieved using CTH preamplifier board (see Figure 6) and no strong positional dependence observed along the counters in terms of light yield (see Figure 7).

4 Conclusion

With Phase-I of COMET set to begin in late 2024, the CTH detector prototype testing is almost complete and construction efforts are already beginning. The beam test results presented here with CTH preamplifier board show performance is expected to meet Phase-I requirements. Improvements to the CTH front-end electronics ongoing to improve signal characteristics and complete integration with trigger electronics system.

Figure 5: Beam test setup used at the Australian Synchrotron. Two prototype CTH counters were placed in line with single 100 MeV electron beam, with two trigger counters placed behind, one on axis and one off axis. Lead shielding was placed around counters and electronics to shield from secondary particles generated and scattered.

Figure 6: Timing distribution of Counter A signals fitted with a Gaussian distribution.

Figure 7: Positional dependence of signal size along Counter A can be seen to be minimal. Measured by taking mean of Landau distribution fit to peak signal voltage distribution at each position (5 cm data shown).

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References

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